

SYSTEMIC AND STRUCTURAL FEATURES OF ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN PHONETIC TERMINOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

This article talks about diachronic terms that are unique in the phonetic system of English and Russian languages. The article consists of an annotation, key words, introduction, main part, conclusion and a list of used literature as required.

Basic concepts: *systemic features, structural features, phonology, semantics, linguistics, synchronic.*

INGLIZ VA RUS FONETIK TERMINOLOGIYASINING TIZIMIK VA TUZILIK XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada ingliz va rus tillarining fonetik tizimida noyob bo'lgan diaxronik atamalar haqida so'z boradi. Maqola izoh, tayanch so'zlar, kirish, asosiy qism, xulosa va talabga muvofiq foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxatidan iborat.

Asosiy tushunchalar: *diaxronik aspektlar, tarixiy o'ziga xoslik, fonologiya, semantika, lingvistika, sinxron.*

When studying terminology from diachronic positions, history is understood as the study of successive changes and development of our knowledge system in certain areas of science, technology, nature, culture, etc.. The diachronic approach to the study of terminology is based on an attempt to overcome the well-known Sossurian dichotomy "synchronicity-diachronicity". Introduced in the early 20th century

emphasizes the contrast between the two ways of considering linguistic phenomena: the study of language at a given moment and the study of linguistic development in its extension in time, and synchronicity is absolutized in its opposition to diachronicity and is proclaimed the only plane in which language can be represented. Undoubtedly, the synchronous analysis, especially in relation to the current state of the language, is easier to implement in practice - due to the greater completeness of factual data and their accessibility. It is easier to check and verify. However, in synchronic linguistic research the language system appears as a fixed static object, a set of ready-made, from nowhere words, word combinations, grammatical structures, phonemes and rigid rules of their combinability. Whereas only the structural-diachronic approach helps to understand how a given language system was formed. Modern systems diachrony extends the theoretical principles of Sossurian antinomy and tries to overcome it. The works of the Prague Linguistic Circle, foreign and domestic linguists determine the following approaches to diachronic and synchronic phenomena. First, systemicity is present in both synchronic and diachronic phenomena; second, diachronic analysis consists in determining the relationship between two successive structures and in establishing relations between them, in other words, it allows one to find out which parts of the preceding system have undergone change. The comparison of consecutive synchronicities reveals the systematicity of diachronic studies. The essence of this antinomy, the principles of which are applied in this study, was most fully expressed by the founder of psychosystematics, G. Guillaume, who noted that language is not only a system, but also a system of systems - diachronic synchronicity. The diachronic approach, using the chronological perspective represented by different states of language, makes it possible to record the changes taking place in language as a process. Language dynamics is defined as a way of functioning (being) of the language family. Language changes in order to continue functioning, though at the same time it can seem unchanged outwardly, as it has to keep up with the changing needs of communication and expression. In all areas of language life there is a development,

artificially divided by researchers into stages, gradually passing from one to the other. The development of terminology is also an ongoing process. Terminological systems, on the one hand, are holistic and stable entities over a period of time. On the other hand, considering the progressive development inherent in science and technology, we can talk about changes in the terminology that serves them: terminological composition expands quantitatively, many terms undergo qualitative shifts in meaning, neologisms appear, some special words are taken out of active use. At the same time, the "patchwork" of terminology is always revealed, which becomes apparent when comparing certain chronological intervals, reflecting different socio-historical and linguistic states and different stages of the formation of terminosystems.

Doublet correspondences of the "word - word combination" type are extremely few in the English phonetic macro-terminological system and account for about 5%. Examples of this type of doublet correspondences are the following series: gliding vowel – **diphthong- дифтонг**, **drum membrane - барабанная мембрана** **tympnum- тимпанум**, **tongue-slip n - slip of the tongue**.

The approach to the study of English phonological terminology applied in this paper implies the study of the processes occurring in terminological semantics from a historical perspective. Therefore, all the identified doublet mono- and polylexemic terminology was analyzed terminology was analyzed from a diachronic point of view.

Examples of doublet terminology that arose: in the chronological periods mentioned above:

XV century - exhalation - выдыхание expiration ;

XVI century - assimilative - assimilatory, caesura - cesura, esophagus - Oesophagus;

XVII century - abrupt - ejective, multisyllabic - polysyllabic , rime - rhyme;

XIX century. - pharyngeal cavities - pharyngeal cavities; rounded - labialized, sonagrams - spectrograms; umlaut ,vowel mutation ;

XX century - false vocal folds - venricular bands, impressionistic transcription - phonetic transcription, flat fricative - s lit fricative, free stress - movable stress ; superfix - suprafix.

Thus, the study of synonymy in English phonetic terminology leads us to the conclusion that this terminosystem is characterized by a constant quantitative growth, achieved largely through the increase in the number of doublets. Their presence in individual terminological systems and in the language of science as a whole is rightly recognized in the linguistic literature as unnecessary and undesirable.

The use in the process of terminological nomination of various linguistic resources, which may include word-formation elements of Greek, Latin, native or other origin.

The parallel functioning of semantically identical mono- and polylexemic terminological formations as a result of lexicalization of term combinations within the English phonological system. Differentiation of term-word variants, arising on various grounds.

To summarize, we can conclude that the processes leading to the emergence of doublets in the terminology of English phonetics have both general and specific (i.e. inherent in terminology as a set of units of special nomination) nature.

Thus, we can conclude that the phonetic structure of monolexemic terminological units of English and Russian phonetics reveals a steady tendency towards complexity, fixed throughout the main periods of the history of the English language.

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